

The first exact locality records from the Turkish Thrace for *Cymatia rogenhoferi* (Fieber, 1864) and *Micronecta pusilla* (Horváth, 1895) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera)

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ABSTRACT: In this study, the first exact locality information of two aquatic Heteroptera species, *Cymatia rogenhoferi* (Corixidae) and *Micronecta pusilla* (Micronectidae), which were previously reported from the Thrace Region but whose locality was unknown, was presented.

KEYWORDS: *Cymatia rogenhoferi*, *Micronecta pusilla*, first exact locality, Turkish Thrace.

INTRODUCTION

A total of 31 species/subspecies (5 of them need confirmation) belonging to 7 genera of the family Corixidae Leach, 1815 have been recorded in Türkiye (Fent et al., 2011). *Cymatia* Flor, 1860, a small genus of Corixidae, is represented by 4 species in the Palearctic Region and so far *Cymatia coleoprata* (Fabricius, 1777) and *Cymatia rogenhoferi* (Fieber, 1864) have been recorded from Türkiye

(Aukema, 2018; Fent et al., 2011). However, records of *C. coleoprata* from Türkiye (Asian part) need confirmation (see Fent et al., 2011).

While *C. rogenhoferi* is known from three localities in Anatolia, its record in Thrace Region is based on Jansson's (1986) markings on the map without specifying the locality. *Micronecta* Kirkaldy, 1897, the only genus of the family Micronectidae Jaczewski, 1924, is represented by 36

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species and 8 subspecies belonging to 8 subgenera in the Palearctic Region (Aukema, 2018). In Türkiye, three species (*M. pusilla*, *M. scholtzi* and *M. griseola*) and three subspecies (*M. anatolica anatolica*, *M. poweri poweri* and *M. wui alkani*) belonging to two subgenera (*Dichaetonecta* and *Micronecta*) are known.

M. poweri poweri was excluded from the Thrace Region Micronectidae list by Fent et al. (2011), and its records from Anatolia need to be confirmed (see Fent et al., 2011). While *M. griseola*, *M. pusilla* and *M. scholtzi* are known from both the Thrace Region and Anatolia, *M. anatolica anatolica* and *M. wui alkani* were recorded only from Anatolia (Fent et al., 2011, Topkara, 2013; Topkara & Ustaoglu, 2014). *M. pusilla* was reported from 6 localities in Anatolia, but was reported from the Thrace Region without locality information (Jansson, 1986, Fent et al., 2011).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the study conducted to determine the aquatic and semi-aquatic Heteroptera fauna of the Thrace Region between 2018-2020, these two species were identified from 4 different aquatic habitats (lake, pond, stream and irrigation pond) in 4 localities belonging to 3 provinces (Edirne, Kırklareli, Tekirdağ). The aquatic forms of *Nepomorpha* infraorder were obtained with the help of plankton scoop from the water and from sand or mud at the water's edge. Jansson (1986) was used in the identification of the species.

RESULTS

NEPOMORPHA Popov, 1968

CORIXOIDEA Leach, 1815

CORIXIDAE Leach, 1815

CYMATIAINAE Walton, 1940

Cymatia Flor, 1860

Cymatia rogenhoferi (Fieber, 1864)

Material examined: Edirne: Uzunköprü - Kurtbey (stream), 41°8'006N 26°35'090E,

53 m, 11.06.2020, 1♀; **Kırklareli:** Kofçaz (irrigation pond), 12.08.2020, 41°56'593N 27°7'685E, 439 m 11♀♀, 12♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: European Türkiye: Without locality information (Jansson, 1986, 1995), Edirne, Kırklareli (this study). Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Konya, Van (Hoberlandt, 1952, Jansson, 1986; Kıyak, 2000; Önder et al., 2006; Koçak & Kemal, 2010; Topkara, 2013).

Distribution in Palearctic: Europe:

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Moldavia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central and South European Territories), Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China (Northern and Northwestern Territories), Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Kirgizia, Mongolia, Russia (West Siberia), Saudi Arabia, Tadjikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. Extralimital: India (Aukema, 2018).

MICRONECTIDAE Jaczewski, 1924

MICRONECTINAE Jaczewski, 1924

Micronecta Kirkaldy, 1897

Micronecta pusilla (Horváth, 1895)

Edirne: Havsa - Ağayeri (lake), 19.05.2018, 41°28'04N 26°57'45E, 76 m, 4♀♀, 3♂♂; **Tekirdağ:** Muratlı - Hanoğlu (pond), 23.05.2018, 41°12'03N 27°22'15E, 111 m, 1♀, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: European Türkiye: Without locality information (Jansson, 1986, 1995), Edirne, Tekirdağ (this study). Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Kayseri, Konya, Sivas, Tokat (Jansson, 1986; Özemi & Önder, 1988; Kıyak, 2000; Fent et al., 2011)

Distribution in Palearctic: Europe:

Bulgaria, Croatia, European Türkiye, Hungary, Moldavia, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iraq, Kirgizia, Syria, Tadjikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2018).

DISCUSSION

In this study conducted between 2018–2020 to determine the aquatic and semi-aquatic Heteroptera fauna in the Thrace Region, the first exact locality records were determined for *Cymatia rogenhoferi* and *Micronecta pusilla* species, which were given by Jansson (1986, 1995) without specifying a definitive locality information. *C. rogenhoferi* is a rare species that has been detected in a small number of localities in the Anatolian part of Türkiye, although it has a wide distribution in Europe and Asia in its Palearctic distribution. In this study, *C. rogenhoferi* specimens were detected in a small stream in Kurtbey village in Edirne-Uzunköprü district and in an irrigation

pond in Kofçaz district of Kırklareli, 2-3 m inland from the shore near the place where the stream feeding the pond flows into the pond. *M. pusilla* is distributed mostly in the Central Anatolian Region of Anatolia. *M. pusilla* specimens were identified in mud and sand in the coastal area of a lake near Ağayeri village of Havsa district of Edirne and a pond in Hanoğlu village of Muratlı district of Tekirdağ.

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